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Valuation of Assets in Banking Activities - Current Situation and Solutions

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Abstract:

In fact, each Vietnamese commercial bank has a different way of valuing assets, the same asset but each bank gives a different valuation result. The valuation of enterprises is also based only on book and balance sheet data, so it is difficult to accurately determine the true value of the business, especially the value of the business as a bank is even more difficult. Valuation because in addition to tangible assets, there are many intangible assets with great value such as: trademarks, patents, traditional products, reputation of the bank's leadership team... The choice of valuation method Accurate asset price, close to the real value of assets or business value, ensuring the interests of the parties will promote debt settlement, debt assignment, purchase, sale, merger, and consolidation transactions. more favorable conditions and contribute to clearing the frozen real estate credit capital, regenerating capital to supply the economy.

Keywords: Valuing assets, bank, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

Recent years have been turbulent years for the economy and banking system. Many challenges are taking place in the scope of macroeconomic management, which has a great impact on the production and business of enterprises and banks. As a result, hundreds of thousands of businesses went bankrupt, and bad debts in banking business increased significantly. It is estimated that about 60% of the value of bad debt of commercial banks is collateral by real estate, accounting for about 180 trillion VND, but the handling of collateral is also facing many difficulties, because each bank is facing many difficulties. Customers have different valuation methods and give different valuation results during asset disposal. Therefore, it is necessary to choose an appropriate valuation method to get objective and accurate results to ensure the interests of the parties involved in transactions with the bank such as: settlement of debts with collateral, an asset mining company acquires, values to sell off assets, or values assets to carry out a bank merger, acquisition, or consolidation (M&A). There are several valuation methods that can be applied in banking: (i) Asset method; (ii) Equity cash flow method; (iii) Market comparison method; (iv) Cost method; (v) Earnings Method and (vi) Business Advantage Method. For Vietnamese commercial banks, intangible assets often account for a large proportion of total bank assets. tangible property. From the current situation of the bank's operational scale, the author only introduces and mentions the use of two main methods of valuing bank assets such as: the asset method and the equity cash flow method. to solve problems related to asset valuation in banking activities.

2. Choosing the right property valuation method

2.1. Asset methods

The asset method is a method of estimating the value of a business based on the market value of total assets of the enterprise minus liabilities, built on the basis of the difference between the market value of assets and assets. Debts of businesses/banks. This method provides a floor price to determine the value of the business/bank to be valued. The asset method can be applied to most types of businesses where the assets of the business are mainly tangible assets.

The basis for enterprise valuation are: documents; accounting books; financial statements of the enterprise for the most recent years; report on inventory of assets, supplies, goods and capital; debt reconciliation record...; Some types of valuation of this method such as based on the sale of the business's assets, based on the liquidation of the assets, based on the net asset value. However, with the assumption that the business is going to be in business, only the net asset value method will be mentioned.

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a) Determination of net worth:

- Based on market price

At that time, net asset value is the selling price of all components of the enterprise's assets on the market (houses, land, machinery, equipment, goods, etc.) at the time of business valuation. business after deducting the debts of the enterprise. The market price is determined for each asset separately.

- Based on book value

Total asset value is determined based on balance sheet data, excluding valueless items such as bad debts. Debts of enterprises include short-term debts, long-term debts, payables to customers, pay for employees, taxes and other payables to the State, payable expenses, internal payables and other debts. other debt. These liabilities are reflected in the capital portion of the enterprise's balance sheet.

b) Determine the value of the advantage:

Advantage value is the immaterial elements that are formed from the intangible assets of the enterprise. With the advantage value, the enterprise can earn a higher profit compared to other enterprises operating in the same industry. The value of advantage is assessed depending on the past achievements as well as the development potential of the business. If the value of advantage has been assessed in the accounting books, it shall be calculated according to the actual balance on the accounting books to calculate the enterprise value. If the value of advantage has not been determined, it shall be calculated based on the average excess profit rate of n years (usually 5 years) adjacent to the time of valuation. Inside:

- Advantages: Using this method is simple, easy to implement, does not require complicated calculation skills, but it cannot completely eliminate subjectivity when calculating the value of the business/bank to be determined. price. The calculation is mainly based on the value on the accounting books, not yet calculating the potential value such as the brand, the future development of the business/bank. With an independent business, a small scale will be effective, time consuming and cost effective.

- Disadvantages: This method has ignored most of the immaterial factors but has real value and sometimes accounts for a very large proportion of the business value, such as: brands, patents, technology, etc. proprietary technology, management level, worker level, reputation, market share... of the enterprise. These may be businesses with insignificant assets but very high profit prospects. With this method, the business is considered as a discrete collection of assets together and does not consider the organic relationship between them. That means evaluating the business in a static state and not as an entity, an existing, operating and developing organization. This method does not provide and build the necessary information base for stakeholders to evaluate the profitability prospects of the enterprise.

- Subjects of application: Usually applied in cases where the stock market has not yet developed or is in the early stages of development; or lack of historical information about the business's performance; or the collection of information to use other valuation methods is difficult and unreliable. Those businesses are either independent or have negative earnings and cash flows forecast. At that time, the enterprise value is merely the liquidation value of the assets. It is difficult for enterprises to predict the future production and business situation.

2.2. Free Cash Flow to Equity method

The equity cash flow method, which is concerned with the total net cash inflows to equity, reflects the profitability of the equity side of the balance sheet.

To calculate the net income in net cash flow, two models are used, the Income Model and the Interest Spread Model. Assume that there is a bank A with a shortened balance sheet (including average lending rate: 15%, average deposit rate: 5%, opportunity cost of money: 9%)

Formula to determine cost of equity:

$$R = R_f + p \times R_p \quad (1.5)$$

Inside:

R_f : Risk-free rate (or risk-free rate of investment)

p : Risk factor

R_p : Risk premium (or market risk rate)

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Advantages: This method appropriately determines profitable cash flows based on working capital, especially in the banking and financial services sector, and reflects the profitability of the Capital side of the Table. Balance Sheet.

Disadvantage: This method is highly dependent on borrowing rates, lending rates (short-term, long-term) and the determination of opportunity costs due to intuition and experience.

Subjects of application: Usually applied to financial service businesses such as investment funds, banks, insurance.

3. Current status of asset valuation of some Vietnamese commercial banks

a) Valuation of bank assets for equitization

Equitization of state-owned enterprises (SOEs) is the transformation of enterprises owned by the State into joint stock companies with mixed owners. The essence of this process is the sale of part or all of the state capital in SOEs to other entities. To be able to sell this capital, a valuation process is required to determine the value of the enterprise, including the value of the State's capital in the enterprise.

In the process of equitization of Vietcombank, Vietinbank, and BIDV banks, bank valuation can be considered as the most important job, takes a lot of time to implement, and valuation results are always a matter of concern for all. Interested managers, businesses and investors. This process is not only purely technical, but also has important socio-economic significance, related to the preservation of the State's capital in the enterprise, the interests of employees, the ability to sell goods and services. shares and ensure the efficiency of production and business activities of the joint stock bank in the future. It can be assessed that the process of valuing banks that are equitized SOEs is still heavy on factors related to the internals of the enterprise, with little attention paid to factors external to the enterprise and the preparation for the pricing and implementation schedule. Currently, the valuation of equitized enterprises is carried out in accordance with Decree 59/2011/ND-CP dated July 18, 2011 of the Government on converting 100% state-owned enterprises into joint stock companies and Circular 202/2011/BTKT-BTC dated December 30, 2011 of the Ministry of Finance guiding the financial handling and determination of enterprise value when converting a 100% state-owned enterprise into a joint stock company in accordance with regulations. Decree No. 59/2011/ND-CP.

Through discussions with some key leaders of equitized SOEs, it is shown that some SOEs use the P/E ratio method. For Vietcombank, Vietinbank, the determination of bank value is calculated by two main methods: the asset method and the discounted cash flow method; At the same time, the K factor factor is considered in comparison with banks that have officially listed prices on the official trading market. In which, the asset method is used the most, however, the result of determining the bank's value by this method is only meaningful as determining the floor price of the bank when the bid starts to join the exchange. stock. For SOEs on the list of equitization, which have taken steps to equitize but are not eligible for equitization, but switch to the form of selling enterprises, the selling enterprise value is taken according to the enterprise value. is determined when performing equitization and is adjusted to deduct the value of assets that the buyer did not buy into the determined enterprise value.

b) Valuation of assets for mortgage, pledge or guarantee for bank loans

Typically when studying asset valuation of Lien Viet Post Commercial Joint Stock Bank, according to Decision No. 3207/2011/HD-LienVietpostbank, dated December 28, 2011 of the General Director of Lien Viet Post Commercial Joint Stock Bank, guiding the Valuation of security assets being real estate is built on the basis of the following provisions: Pursuant to Civil Code No. 33/2005/QH11 dated June 16, 2005 of the National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam. Vietnamese meaning; Pursuant to the Land Law No. 13/2003/QH11 dated November 26, 2003 and guiding documents; Pursuant to the Law on Construction No. 16/2003/QH11 dated November 26, 2003 and guiding documents; Pursuant to the Law on Housing No. 56/2005/QH11 dated November 29, 2005 and guiding documents; Pursuant to the Government's Decree No. 163/2006/ND-CP dated December 29, 2006 on security transactions and related amendments and supplements; Pursuant to Decree No. 83/2010/ND-CP dated July 23, 2010 of the Government on Registration of Secured Transactions; Circular No. 203/2009/TT-BTC guiding the management and use of fixed asset depreciation; Pursuant to the Decision on Promulgating the Regulation on Loan Security No.

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141/2011/QĐ-HĐQT dated April 5, 2011 of the Board of Directors; Pursuant to the Loan Guarantee Regulation No. 1774/2011/QĐ-LienVietPostBank dated August 25, 2011;

When studying the property valuation of Vietnam Import-Export Commercial Joint Stock Bank (Eximbank), there are current regulations: Valuation of real estate (real estate) to ensure loans of Eximbank is the determination or re-determination of the value of real estate. value of the real estate in accordance with the market at one location at the time of signing the security contract for the real estate used to secure the loan by the appropriate method. The appraisal of the value of real estate is one of the bases for Eximbank to consider and approve the loan level by means of collateral. The loan amount is calculated in combination with the consideration of market stability, which is also considered as the asset price to handle the collateral, offsetting the bank loan when the customer fails to repay the loan. . Valuation of land use rights must comply with Decree No. 85/CP-ND/2002, dated October 25, 2002 of the Government, which is the actual transfer price in the locality at the time of appraisal. The appraisal of property prices is carried out according to the following documents: Decree 101/2005/ND-CP on valuation, Circular 17/2005/TT-BTC guiding Decree 101/2005/ND-CP, Decision No. Decision 29/2008/QĐ-BTC on the issuance of 6 valuation criteria (phase 3). The standard construction price list for all types of architecture is applied according to the price list issued by the competent authorities of the province or city where the real estate is located to be appraised. Which method to use for valuation depends on the characteristics of the real estate to be appraised. Particularly, the appraisal of real estate prices to secure loans from Eximbank is carried out by direct comparison method or surplus method:

The direct comparison method is the method of using market transaction documents of real estates with similar characteristics to the real estate to be appraised to determine the market price of this real estate. When conducting price appraisal by direct comparison method, it is necessary to search for real estate information - at least 02 real estates - that have been traded on the market at a time close to the time of valuation (within 3 months), to conduct analysis and compare the similarities and differences between them with the real estate to be appraised, so that appropriate price adjustments can be made to determine the market value of the real estate to be appraised.

The residual method is a valuation method in which the market value of the property to be appraised is determined based on the existing capital value by taking the estimated value of the hypothetical development of the asset (total value of assets). revenue) minus all costs incurred to generate that growth. The valuation of real estate by the residual method is applied according to the following formula:

Real Estate Market Value Appraisal = Development Revenue - Development Cost

The residual method is applied to assess the value of real estate with potential for development.

The valuation of assets of companies and banks listed on the stock exchange is also in line with the regulations on asset valuation of Eximbank in investment and trading in securities, as well as the sale of Eximbank's shares at a stock exchange. the number of joint stock commercial banks that Eximbank has contributed capital as an owner in recent years.

c) Valuation of assets for banking M&A

Through actual research on mergers and acquisitions of joint stock commercial banks, it is found that the typical asset valuation of Saigon Commercial Joint Stock Bank (consolidation of 3 Saigon - De Nhat - Vietnam Tin Nghia Commercial Joint Stock Banks, Feb. /2012) in this activity is regulated and has some characteristics as follows:

Stemming from the point of view of the owners of the 3 banks, a number of representative groups of shareholders own shares in these banks, so the revaluation of the assets of the 3 banks is easy to agree with. the asset values of each bank. Take the data of each item on the balance sheet of each bank and add them together on the balance sheet to form the general balance sheet of the bank after the merger or consolidation; agreed that the valuation of credit lending assets of each individual bank was similar before, without the need to re-valuate the collateral or guarantee the bank; agreed to value the shares of the three banks equally at the ratio 1:1:1.

From the reality of the business activities of the three banks above, after merging into Saigon Commercial Joint Stock Bank, the development of a common standard process for bank asset valuation and collateral valuation for banks to Loans and guarantees are as follows: The asset valuation process at Saigon Commercial Joint Stock Bank is issued according to Decision No. 62/2012/QĐ-SCB-TGD dated June 18,

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2012 by the General Director of SCB. , according to the decision to show some of the following contents: ISO 9001:2008 standard; Decision 129/2008/QĐ-BTC, dated December 31, 2008 on the promulgation of 06 valuation standards; Circular 203/2009/TT-BTC dated October 20, 2009 of the Ministry of Finance promulgating guidelines on the regime of management, use and depreciation of fixed assets; Decision of the People's Committee of the province/city on the issuance of annual land prices; other relevant legal documents.

In fact, in the process of merging and consolidating Vietnam Tin Nghia Commercial Joint Stock Bank, First Commercial Joint Stock Bank into Saigon Commercial Joint Stock Bank, in order to have Saigon Commercial Joint Stock Bank as it is today, the share conversion price between banks goods in the ratio 1:1:1; acknowledge the business results after being independently audited and there is almost a high consensus on the arrangement and re-use of human resources for the bank after the merger or consolidation. The favorable factor is that these 3 banks all have the same number of main shareholders, the same business purpose and motto, and fall into the situation of voluntary merger and consolidation at the suggestion of the State Bank, if not the same. required merger and consolidation in the current period. These are the three joint stock commercial banks that carry out the first consolidation mission according to the roadmap to increase their charter capital to at least VND 3,000 billion in 2012.

4. General assessment of bank asset valuation

- There is no general legal framework on asset valuation in banking activities; especially in banking mergers, consolidation and acquisitions, mainly banks agree to agree with each other in different ways of valuing banks.

- There is no reference base system for enterprise valuation and the technical complexity makes it difficult to refer to coefficients and indexes to apply to the banking valuation method of organizations. Different consulting organizations will give different valuation results.

- Each bank has a different method of valuing assets, so it is difficult to compare and accurately determine the actual total assets of the bank, based only on the figures recorded on the balance sheet of the bank. each bank for evaluation. The method of determining the value of the collateral is different and the loan-to-collateral ratio is also different: some banks apply up to 85% of the property value, but there are also banks that only lend up to a maximum of 85% of the property value. 70% of the market value (except the price bracket set by the state for provinces/cities/localities) or as much as 2 times the price of each type of land, the location of the land in the state land price bracket set by the Provincial People's Committee/ The city's regulations... proved to be inadequate, overlapping, and inconsistently valuing the same property, house and land in each bank, giving a different result.

- The criteria and accounting regime for the revaluation of bank assets have not yet been established, which changes in reality from year to year according to the public financial reporting regime, and there is no basis for accounting for the increase or decrease in the value of assets. bank fixed.

- For bank assets that are machinery, equipment, and goods, the valuation is based on the value of VAT invoices, import and export of goods, through depreciation to evaluate the residual value.

- The majority of Vietnamese commercial banks in general and joint stock commercial banks in particular have not been publicly listed on the stock exchange.

- Banking M&A activities are still new to the Vietnamese market, with few typical large deals, so there are few lessons learned for the valuation of bank assets in M&A activities, but the valuation of assets. Bank intangibles have a very practical meaning.

- The handling of outstanding debts is still difficult, especially the handling of bad debts takes a lot of time and effort due to the lack of synchronous and close coordination of the banking, tax, finance, and ministry sectors. Construction, Court, Judgment Execution; on the other hand, there are many limitations on the mechanism to monitor the results of bank asset valuation, progress and quality of bank valuation.

5. Some solutions and recommendations

Stemming from the current situation of asset valuation activities related to banks, the author would like to have some recommended solutions as follows:

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a) Group of solutions from the state

Firstly, focus and systematically develop legal provisions on commercial bank acquisition, merger and consolidation in the Law on Credit Institutions as definitions, concepts, form, conditions, process, pricing.

Second, to develop a standard process for valuing assets of state-owned commercial banks conducting equitization, joint-stock commercial banks with financial support from the State in mergers, consolidation and acquisition activities. bank acquisition.

Third, synchronizing the contents of documents between relevant Laws regulating the methods and methods of valuing assets of enterprises and banks.

Summarizing the valuation of state-owned commercial banks in the recent equitization process of Vietcombank, Vietinbank, and BIDV shows that the lesson to be learned is to step by step speed up the process of building a complete legal framework for valuation. banks, improve conditions and legal environment in a timely manner to issue a valuation framework for SOEs that are state-owned commercial banks, in terms of potentiality through valuation of banking assets and M&A activities that create The main source of capital for the stock market. It is necessary to synchronize the standards on the process and methods of valuing corporate assets in general and valuing bank assets in particular in M&A transactions in order to establish accurate and objective asset values, creating favorable conditions for investors. accelerate the process of bank mergers, consolidation and acquisitions.

Fourth, build a reference base on asset valuation connecting the State Bank's Credit Information Center (CIC), General Department of Taxation and Tax Departments directly managing businesses for M&A activities. bank on bank asset valuation

Bank valuation methods require a complete and accurate volume of information provided by CIC such as information on credit rating coefficients, financial and banking ratios, stock indexes and tables. balance the bank's assets; The price of the property to be appraised must be linked to the actual price following the market through the market bulletin on real estate prices developed by the State (it can be assigned to the Ministry of Finance to assume the prime responsibility for the construction to serve as a basis for collecting transfer tax). , purchase and sale of assets, etc.). In fact, the CIC still needs to continue to perfect the development and supplement standards to provide accurate information for the banking system to use. Determine the market value, which is the bank's actual value that both buyers and sellers can accept. In particular, in the equitization process of State-owned commercial banks, the seller of shares is the State, and the buyers of shares are employees of the bank and shareholders outside the bank. Therefore, the value of the enterprise must be reasonably determined by an appropriate scientific method, in accordance with reality, and fully consider the valuation of intangible assets, only then can it be guaranteed. a harmonious combination between the interests of the State, enterprises, investors and employees in the bank.

Fifth, speeding up the process of completing the valuation and auction of bank shares through market M&A activities and foreign investors' holding rates, standardizing the regulatory ratio and making it public. The transparency of the valuation process is a very important basis for determining the bank's value before listing shares on the stock exchange.

Conducting bank stock auctions in business valuation. The organization of a public auction of banks through the Auction Center at the stock market will create great interest in the investment public, and the State will receive capital to restructure the economy according to orientation.

Sixth, to develop a standard process for selecting reputable organizations, ethical standards for practice, and standards for valuation to apply to bank valuation.

Agreeing to select reputable organizations to value banking assets like choosing the list of auditing companies to audit the Vietnamese commercial banking system in the past. In fact, in Vietnam, this field is still new in both theory and practice because the economy is in the process of transitioning to a market economy, and there are no specific quantitative criteria for selection, especially financial resources. intangible product. Therefore, the establishment of Credit Rating Agency (CRA) is an intermediary organization, independent operation specializing in risk assessment of economic sectors and investment programs of the Government. . Valuation objects are financial institutions, banks, insurance, non-banking institutions, corporations and corporations, large-scale businesses listed on the stock market.

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The assessment of credit rating as well as risk of CRA helps banks more convenient when appraising loans for businesses and projects. As for investors, based on the results of CRA, investors have a basis to re-evaluate, forecast the development of the bank, and determine the stock price to make investment decisions.

b) Group of solutions from commercial banks

Bank valuation is the valuation of the assets and property rights of the bank. When performing asset valuation in banking M&A activities, it is necessary to accurately identify tangible assets and intangible assets of the bank.

Firstly, commercial banks need to systematize the types of tangible and intangible assets of the bank and at the same time choose an asset valuation method that is suitable to the characteristics of their bank's assets in order to evaluate their assets. the correct asset value or the overall value of the bank.

Experience shows that the valuation of bank assets in M&A activities is usually using two methods of assets and equity cash flow. In particular, in banking activities, intangible assets account for a large proportion of the total value of the bank, so when valuing assets, it is necessary to fully evaluate and have an overview of this volume of assets.

Second, publicly and transparently disclose financial statements before conducting bank valuation.

The value of the bank, progress and quality of the valuation depends a lot on the truthfulness, completeness and accuracy of the data, information and reasonableness of the valued financial statements. The State needs to have regulations that compel the accounting and financial statements of banks to develop according to some basic international standards approved by the State Securities Commission for participation in the stock market.

Third, through experience and analysis of the current situation of valuation, it is found that when participating in M&A activities, banks should choose asset valuation methods and equity cash flow methods to value assets. Banks will be more accurate.

The two methods of valuing assets and equity cash flow have many advantages as described in the previous section. When valuing, attention should be paid to the valuation of intangible assets. On the other hand, the application of these methods is suitable with the actual operating status of the Vietnamese commercial banking system in the current period. However, other methods should also be cautious and consider more in the process of valuing bank assets to have more accurate valuation results and valuation of bank assets.

Fourth, banks themselves carry out financial sanitization and deal with bad debts before valuing banks.

Banks need to clearly identify objective and subjective causes to take measures to deal with bad debts according to regulations, quickly have solutions to make the financial healthy, when we get the results, we can easily identify the bad debt. accurately determine the offering value and conduct favorable banking M&A transactions.

Fifth, the buyer and the seller must comply with the law on M&A transactions.

Parties conducting an M&A transaction must be transparent in financial, accounting data, and objectives mentioned in the offering process; On the buyer side, investors also need to be transparent about their financial situation and purchase needs in accordance with the law; commits not to have speculative and profiteering factors that affect the business activities of the bank offering shares and shares.

Sixth, the bank parties focus on valuing loans and collateral before deciding on M&A transactions.

In the valuation process, above all asset quality, the reason these backed contracts are so attractive is not only because of the low cost, but also because of the government guarantee of the policy. M&A policy in banking activities. Practical experience for potential buyers is to understand their ability to re-evaluate the loan business. Working with buyers to really help them handle the quality of loans and collateral, especially the ability to recover bad debts, is a key factor in helping the bank to deliver the transaction. Successful translation in M&A activities.

Seventh, for banks that do not meet the criteria to continue operating, they are forced to value their assets in accordance with the State's regulations for liquidation and comply with the Bankruptcy Law in order to contribute to a healthy banking system. row.

The basic roadmap for domestic joint stock commercial banks on M&A is also available, for those banks that do not meet the prescribed charter capital for each period, have serious liquidity shortages and are

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unable to pay customers. If banks do not comply with regulations on working capital adequacy, or do not comply with regulations on banking inspection and supervision, it is recommended that the State Bank should take strong action to handle and conduct valuation of bank assets, in order to bankruptcy in order to contribute to a healthy banking system.

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